

DITOs Pan-European Policy Round table on citizen science and DIY science

DITOs FINAL EVENT

Royal Belgian Institute
of Natural Sciences
Brussels | Belgium

APRIL 3rd 2019

**doing it
together
science**

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WHAT IS DITOs?

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT

Doing It Together Science (DITOs) has organised many innovative events across Europe focusing on the active involvement of citizens in **citizen science**. In Doing It Together Science, universities and research institutions worked together with science galleries, museums and art institutions to engage people with citizen science in Europe. More than 700 innovative workshops, exhibitions, and activities were organised in 13 countries in Europe. With this project the eleven European partners demonstrated to show that citizen science is an accessible and fun way to explore the world around you.

WHO ARE THE PARTNERS OF DITOs?

A pan-European network (European Citizen Science Association), SMEs (Tekiu; eutema), universities (University College London; Universite Paris Descartes; University of Geneva), science galleries, museums and arts organisations (Kapelica Gallery / Kersnikova; Medialab-Prado; Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences) and NGOs (Meritum Association; Waag Society). These organisations cross multiple countries and languages, enabling coverage of much of Europe in its native languages. This eleven partner project was coordinated by the Extreme Citizen Science Group at University College London (UCL).

KEY FACTS

OVER
700
EVENTS

577,019
PARTICIPANTS

2,9 million
ONLINE
INTERACTIONS

50,8%
FEMALE
PARTICIPATION

DITOs FINAL EVENT

3rd April 2019 from 9:00 to 20:00

Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, 29 rue Vautier 1000 Brussels, Belgium

9:00 - 9:30	Registration
9:30 - 9:40	Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Camille Pisani, RBINS
9:40 - 10:00	Opening <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Muki Haklay, UCL Linden Farrer, European Commission
10:00 - 11:00	DITOs project results Partners presenting different elements of the project Moderated by Margaret Gold, ECSA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nadia Richman, UCL - The DITOs consortium escalator Gaia Agnello, ECSA - Environmental sustainability Imane Baiz, UPD - Biodesign Pawel Wyszomirski, Meritum - European Clean Air Day and citizen science for air quality Carole Paleco, RBINS - The Museum of natural sciences & Citizen Science Simon Gmajner, Kersnikova - Bridging the Gap Ted Fjallman, Tekiu - Discovery trips Claudia Göbel, ECSA - Policy engagement for RRI Cindy Regalado, Tekiu and Pawel Miedzinski, Eutema interviewing DITOs participant journeys: Adam Timlett, Pen-Yu an Hsing, Bernard McGlinchey, Roland van Dierendonck, Mark Langtry

11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 12:30	Doing it together beyond DITOs How DITOs legacy is taken forward by other projects. Short talks to demonstrate the level of R&D investment in citizen science/observatories and the level of scientific interest. Moderated by Colombe Warin, Project Adviser, European Commission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rosa Arias, D-NOSES, Ibercivis Maria Zolotonosa, SPARKS & VOICES, ECSITE Marzia Mazzonetto, EU-Citizen.Science, ECSA Uta Wehn, WeObserve & Ground Truth 2.0, IHE Delft Balázs Bálint, National strategies, Environmental Social Science Research Group
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch
13:00 - 17:00	Marketplace A space to bring ideas of iconic tools, strategies from partners and other projects, ECSA Working Groups, citizen scientists and a corner for B2B as part of the Discovery Trip.
14:00 - 15:15	Taking the Journey roundtables Theme-based tables for sharing lessons learnt about DITOs activities. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy engagement, ECSA and Tekiu Event design, planning and organising, Kersnikova, UPD Reaching the unreachable - designing and organising the Science bus and XperiLab, WS, RBINS How to bring people together to work on a common goal, Medialab Prado, Meritum Project coordination, cross-pollinating projects, and how to stay friends, UCL Methods to evaluate outreach events, Eutema, Tekiu CS integration within an organisation, RBINS, UNIGE
15:15 - 15:30	Coffee break

PARALLEL POLICY ROUNDTABLES

15:30 - 17:00

Citizen science & environmental monitoring and reporting

Policy roundtable aiming at collecting input and feedback on guidelines for citizen science & environmental monitoring – document prepared by the European Commission (DG Environment, DG Research and Innovation, JRC, EEA...) to be available at the end of 2019. This session is part of the EC consultation process.

Moderated by Sven Schade, Joint Research Centre

Key speakers:

- Kim De Rijck, DG Environment;
- Marjan Van Meerloo, DG Research and Innovation
- Izabela Freytag, EASME

15:30 - 17:00

Citizen science support for the science-policy interface

This DITOs-BiodivERsA joint roundtable is aimed at researchers, practitioners and policy-makers, with any level of experience and knowledge of citizen science. The participants will be divided into three groups and invited to reflect on three main aspects of citizen science support to Science-Policy Interfacing. The outcomes of the discussions will be compiled into a short, practical toolkit to be published in the aftermath of the workshop. Groups will be switching tables and have the opportunity to address each aspect:

Table A: Citizen science in support of excellent and societal/policy-relevant research.

Moderated by Frédéric Lemaitre, BiodivERsA & Claire Bléry, BiodivERsA secretariat

Table B: Practical tools and resources for Citizen science.

Moderated by Hilde Eggermont, BiodivERsA, Belgian Biodiversity Platform & Angélique Berhault, Belgian Biodiversity Platform

Table C: Researchers' needs related to Citizen science.

Moderated by Sonia Vanderhoeven, Science officer, Belgian Biodiversity Platform & Lise Goudeseune, Science officer, Belgian Biodiversity Platform

17:00 - 17h30

Wrap up & Closing remarks

- Philippe Galiay, European Commission

17:30

Cocktail

20:00

End

| MEZZANINE |
|---|---|---|---|--|
| Welcome coffee
9:00 - 9:30 | | | | |
| | Opening
9:30 - 10:00 | | | |
| | DITOs project results
10:00 - 11:00 | | | |
| Coffee break
11:00 - 11:30 | | | | |
| | Doing it together beyond DITOs
11:30 - 12:30 | | | |
| Lunch
12:30 - 14:00 | | | | |
| | | Market Place
13:00 - 17:00 | Taking the Journey
14:00 - 15:15 | |
| | | | Parallel policy roundtables
15:30 - 17:00 | |
| | Wrap up & closing remarks
17:00 - 17:30 | | | |
| | | | | Cocktail
17:30 - 20:00 |

VENUE MAPS

FLOOR -1

FLOOR 0

MARKET PLACE EXHIBITORS

AALBORG UNIVERSITY

The field of the Department of Planning at Aalborg University includes development and planning in a broad sense, reaching from the social science aspects of development to physical planning, land management, and to technical subjects such as road engineering.

👉 **Contact: Michael Sogaard Jorgensen**

CITIZEN SCIENCE IRELAND

Citizen Science Ireland arranges venues for people to learn collectively and in participatory environments. It organises hackathons and coding clubs, competitions and events for the older members of the community. It even runs the Irish Computer and Communications Museum of Ireland.

👉 **Contact: Martin Serrano**

D-NOSES

D-NOSES (Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability) aims to provide an inclusive, bottom-up approach to tackle odour pollution issues through the empowerment of citizens and co-creation of solutions with all involved stakeholders.

👉 **Contact: Simone Rüfenacht**

EU-CITIZEN.SCIENCE

EU-Citizen.Science is a three-year EU-funded project that will create a sustainable platform and mutual learning space for citizen science in Europe. The platform will also be a knowledge-sharing portal, a training network and a support community for citizen science across Europe.

👉 **Contact: Marzia Mazzonetto**

EUROPEAN CLEAN AIR DAY

European Clean Air Day - an ECSA Working Group initiative - calls for a Europe-wide Clean Air Day to be organised annually, starting from 20th June 2019. The primary focus of the action is to engage citizens in doing science on air pollution across Europe.

👉 **Contact: Pawel Wyszomirski**

EUROPEAN COMMISSION - DG RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

This EU Commission department is responsible for EU policy on research, science and innovation, with a view to help create growth and jobs and tackle our biggest societal challenges.

👉 **Contact: Josefina Enfedaque**

IJEDEREEN WETENSCHAPPER

Iedereen Wetenschapper (Everybody Scientist) is the platform for citizen science in Flanders and The Netherlands. It calls on citizens to participate in 200+ citizen science projects, via a website, social media and a newsletter.

👉 **Contact: Liesbeth Gijssels**

KERSNIKOVA

Kersnikova Institute is the institutional frame for Kapelica Gallery, is a platform for contemporary investigative arts, with the hacker space Rampa, where relations between society, science, technology and art are being reconsidered, and the laboratory BioTehna, which focuses on the artistic research of living systems.

👉 **Contact: Simon Gmajner**

PARENTING SCIENCE GANG

Parenting Science Gang is a user-led citizen science project working with parenting groups on Facebook collecting questions parents want a scientific answer to. Then with help from scientists each group has designed and run their own experiment to answer that question.

👉 **Contact: Sophia Collins**

PIBINKO

The pibinko.org network has been operating since 2006 on the protection and promotion of lesser known resources in the fields of culture, environment, and open innovation, with a focus on community engagement.

👉 **Contact: Andrea Giacomelli**

SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE SERVICES

Scientific Knowledge Services is advocating for citizen science since 2015 through a series of events called Focus on Open Science (focusopenscience.org). A broader engagement between science and society can speed up the processes that lead to knowledge, understanding and innovation.

👉 **Contact: Tiberius Ignat**

UNIVERSITÉ PARIS DESCARTES / CRI PARIS

Sitting at the crossroads of research and education, the Center for Research and Interdisciplinarity (CRI) experiments and spreads new ways of learning, teaching, conducting research and mobilizing collective intelligence in life, learning and digital sciences.

👉 **Contact: Tonino Rizzo**

XperiBIRD

XperiBIRD.be is an educational project supported by Google.org conducted by the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences since 2016. It aims to distribute nest boxes equipped with a camera to schools across Belgium, allowing children to follow the nesting of garden birds and report on their observations to an ornithologist based at the RBINS.

👉 **Contact: Wendy Massart**

XperiLAB

XperiLAB.be is a science truck, a mobile laboratory that criss-crosses Belgium to help arouse people's interest in science. XperiLAB.be is designed specifically for children from 10 to 14 years old.

👉 **Contact: Alice Jones**

DITOs PARTNERS

ECSA

The European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) is a non-profit organisation set up to encourage the growth of the citizen science movement in Europe in order to enhance the participation of the general public in scientific processes. Since its establishment in 2013, ECSA has been growing at a fast pace reaching over 250 individual and organisational members from across Europe and beyond. ECSA Headquarter, hosted at the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, is a dynamic and diverse team committed to supporting the development of citizen science in Europe and beyond. We engage and support our members and non-members in a great diversity of activities promoted through working groups and participation in a number of Horizon 2020 projects.

<https://ecs.citizen-science.net/>

EUTEMA

Eutema is a strategic research management consultancy from Vienna. eutema has managed research initiatives and prepared research and innovation strategies for more than 15 years. It focuses on information technology and biosciences and is an expert in the evaluation of research and innovation measures.

<https://eutema.com/>

KERSNIKOVA

Kersnikova Institute is a non-profit and non-governmental cultural organisation, founded by the Student Organisation of the University of Ljubljana, and serves as an institutional frame for three progressive venues: Kapelica Gallery, a world renowned platform for contemporary investigative arts, the hacker space Rampa, where relations between society, science, technology and art are being reconsidered, and the inspirational laboratory BioTehna, which focuses on the artistic research of living systems. Over twenty years of daily activities have resulted in hundreds of unforgettable moments and experiences, which have given the contemporaneity form and meaning. Kersnikova Institute is due to its strong programme focus marked on the maps of the most interesting international centres dealing with contemporary investigative arts, science and cutting-edge technologies.

<http://kersnikova.org/>

MEDIALAB PRADO

MEDIALAB PRADO - MP

Medialab Prado is a citizens' laboratory that serves as a place of encounter for the production of open cultural projects. Anybody can make proposals or sign up for proposals made by someone else and carry them out on a collaborative basis. Activities are structured around work groups, open calls for the production of projects, collaborative research and learning communities that address a very wide range of topics.

Our goals are to build, promote and sustain learning and hands-on communities to work together; to experiment, improve and evaluate collaborative work methodologies; to open up spaces for critical reflection on digital technology and its impact on society.

<https://www.medialab-prado.es/>

MERITUM

The Center for Training and Personal Development MERITUM is a Polish association founded in 1999. Its mission is to build civil society and improve the quality of human resources with respect for principles of sustainable development. MERITUM is created by high-ranked professionals and volunteers. The Association has extensive experience in the implementation of training projects. Since 2006 almost 600 people graduated from MERITUM School of Trainers, a 9th months learning programme for professional trainers (level 5, EQF – European Qualification Framework). Important part of MERITUM philosophy is DIY approach. Participants of projects and School of Trainers not only learn but are also responsible for leading their own small projects within their communities.

<https://meritum.slask.pl/>

ROYAL BELGIAN INSTITUTE OF NATURAL SCIENCES

The RBINS is a federal scientific institution situated in Brussels. It hosts numerous associations each devoted to a specific research domain and gathering both scientists and non-scientists. These associations represent one of the assets of the Institute as a central hub fostering exchanges between research and citizens and developing citizen science activities and projects. The Institute runs a Science Truck called XperiLAB and interacts remotely with schools through the XperiBIRD programme. The Institute has organised the first focused Bioblitz in Brussels in 2018 and runs small touring exhibitions related to biodiversity. It has organised its 1st citizen science day end of 2018 which has strengthened the connections between citizen scientists and promoted their contributions and work.

<https://www.naturalsciences.be/>

TEKIU

Tekiu Ltd is a UK SME in the business of knowledge transfer, fact-finding missions, international benchmarking, and facilitating R&D partnerships. We engage with customers from diverse industries and geographies with focus areas such as on health & life sciences, research and innovation systems, social policy, environmental technology, and smart cities. We assist our clients in identifying innovation gaps and answering the important questions that help them thrive and respond to the challenges of tomorrow. We do this through bespoke 'Tekiu Discovery Trips' to expose clients to a range of perspectives and gain valuable insights. For DITOs, Tekiu engaged key decision- and policy-makers in local public authorities to visit our partner organisations, learn about the value of active citizen engagement, and gain hands-on experience of issues within the project themes of environmental sustainability and biodesign.

<http://www.tekiu.com/>

UNIVERSITÉ DE GENÈVE - UNIGE

The Bioscope is the public laboratory of the University of Geneva devoted to education in biomedicine and the life sciences for school children and the general public. Part of the larger ScienScope, its goal is to improve scientific literacy, foster a critical dialogue about science and society, and develop innovative outreach methods. The activities offered represent an opportunity for the public to meet practicing scientists, learn about the latest results of scientific research, and explore the nature of science and scientific inquiry.

<https://www.unige.ch/>

UCL EXTREME CITIZEN SCIENCE

(ExCiteS) research group brings together scholars from diverse fields to develop and contribute to the guiding theories, tools and methodologies that will enable any community to start a citizen science project to deal with issues that concern them. With an interdisciplinary research approach, we aim to provide any user, regardless of their background or literacy level, with a set of tools that can be used to collect, analyse and act on information according to agreed-upon scientific methods. The group have extensive experience in designing, implementing, and leading participatory research projects in many areas, with funding from UK funders (such as the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council), FP7 and Horizon 2020, as well as working with NGOs and commercial bodies.

<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/> 🌟

UPD / CRI PARIS

The Center for Research and Interdisciplinarity (CRI) experiments and spreads new ways of learning, teaching, conducting research and mobilizing collective intelligence in life, learning and digital sciences. Sitting at the crossroads of research and education, CRI advocates for innovative pedagogy putting the student at the heart of their own learning experience through projects, research and societal challenges. CRI develops educational and research programs, from newborn to PhD including lifelong learning, together with the Sorbonne Paris Cité University, Paris Descartes University and Paris Diderot University. CRI develops programs with international partners, where students follow stimulating programs through a learning by doing approach, as well as entrepreneurial projects inspired by the 17 Social Development Goals established by the United Nations.

<https://cri-paris.org/> 🌟

WAAG

Waag operates at the intersection of science, technology and the arts. Waag focuses on emergent technologies as instruments of social change, and is guided by the values of fairness, openness and inclusivity. Waag conducts research in both imaginative and practical terms, addressing its fellow citizens from a position of equality and collaboration. The DITOs Science Bus hosted many DIY workshops all around Europe to engage curious minds and encourage people to share their life hacks. The bus stopped at festivals, campsites and marketplaces. Waag prepared handy instructions and (research) tools to build simple scientific instruments. Science for everyone! In Amsterdam, Waag held multiple series of Do-it-together biology workshops and discussion nights to unravel the latest biotech taboos and explore our own morals.

<https://waag.org/> 🌟

SPEAKERS

Camille Pisani | RBINS

Muki Hacklay | UCL

Linder Farrer | EC

Margaret Gold | ECSA

Nadia Richman | UCL

Gaia Agnello | ECSA

Imane Baïz | UPD

Paweł Wyszomirski | Meritum

Carole Paleco | RBINS

Simon Gmajner | Kersnikova

Ted Fjallman | Tekiu

Claudia Göbel | ECSA

Cindy Regalado | Tekiu

Paweł Miedzinski | Eutema

Colombe Warin | EC

Rosa Arias | Ivercivis

Maria Zolotonosa | ECSITE

Marzia Mazzonetto | ECSA

Uta Wehn | IHE Delft

Bálint Balázs | ESSRG

Sven Schade | JRC

Kim De Rijck | DG Environment

Marjan Van Meerloo | DG Research and Innovation

Izabela Freytag | EASME

Frédéric Lemaître | BiodivERSa

Claire Bléry | BiodivERSa

Hilde Eggermont | BiodivERSa

Angélique Berhault | Belgian Biodiversity Platform

Sonia Vanderhoeven | Belgian Biodiversity Platform

Lise Goudeseune | Belgian Biodiversity Platform

Philippe Galiay | EC

